

A Kinetic Investigation of the Oxidation of Some 1, 3-Diols by Permanganate in Acid Media

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The oxidation of 1,3-propanediol, 1,3-butanediol and 2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol by acid permanganate, in the presence of pyrophosphate, is of first order with respect to each of permanganate, the diol and hydrogen ion. Pyrophosphate ion decreases the rate but to a limiting value. The reaction leads to the formation of cleavage products. The activation parameters have been evaluated. A mechanism in which the first step is the rapid reversible formation of a complex between the substrate and Mn(III) or Mn(IV), followed by the C—C bond rupture in the rate determining step has been suggested.

OXIDATION of 1,2-diols by acid permanganate has recently been reported by us¹. The oxidation of 1,3-diols by acid permanganate has, however, not received any attention. Therefore, the present investigation was taken up. The paper describes the kinetics of the oxidation of 1,3-propanediol, 1,3-butanediol and 2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol by acid permanganate.

Experimental

Materials: Diols (B.D.H.) were distilled under reduced pressure before use. Perchloric acid (Riedel) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Sodium perchlorate (Riedel) was used to adjust the ionic strength. All other chemicals used were analytical grade reagents.

The experimental procedures have been described earlier¹. The rate constants reported are mean of multiple runs and are reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

Induced reduction of mercuric chloride: Acid permanganate oxidation of these diols induces reduction of mercuric chloride. This indicates the formation of a reducing intermediate, i.e., a free radical.

Product Analysis: For product analysis, reaction mixtures containing excess of the diol and other requisite reagents were left overnight to ensure complete reduction of permanganate. Characterisation by different spot tests² show that 1,3-propanediol gives formaldehyde and acetaldehyde, 1,3-butanediol gives acetaldehyde and 2-methyl 2,4-pentanediol acetone.

Rate Laws: When the diol is in excess, the rate at which permanganate disappears follows first order rate laws. The rate of oxidation is also proportional to the concentration of the diol and of hydrogen ions at constant ionic strength.

Effect of Mn(II): The rate of oxidation of these diols are affected by addition of manganous ions. The addition of Mn(II) causes a decrease in the oxidation rate (Table 1).

Increase in the concentration of sodium pyrophosphate decreases the oxidation rate but soon reaches a limiting value, at pyrophosphate concentration = 2.5×10^{-2} moles/litre, and further addition of pyrophosphate has no effect.

Effect of Temperature: The oxidation of these diols have been studied at different temperatures (Table 2) and activation parameters evaluated. The specific rate constant, k , is defined as: $k = k_1/[\text{diol}][\text{H}^+]$. The errors limited in the values of ΔH^* and ΔS^* are ± 1.0 kcal/mole and ± 2.0 e.u. respectively.

TABLE 1. EFFECT OF Mn(II) ON THE REACTION RATE AT 35°C

	[KMnO ₄], $8.0 \times 10^{-4}M$; [Na ₂ Py], $6.6 \times 10^{-2}M$						
(a) [1,3 Propanediol]	$1 \times 10^{-2}M$						
(b) [1,3 Butanediol]	$1 \times 10^{-2}M$						
(c) [2-methyl 2,4 Pentanediol]	$5 \times 10^{-2}M$						
		[H ⁺]	0.92M				
		[H ⁺]	0.94M				
		[H ⁺]	0.80M				
$10^4[\text{Mn(II)}]M$	0.0	4.0	8.0	12.0	16.0	20.0	30.0
$10^3 k_1$ (min ⁻¹)							
(a)	15.4	16.0	15.0	14.3	6.6	4.4	2.3
(b)	15.1	15.0	14.0	12.0	6.8	5.3	2.1
(c)	18.6	18.0	17.0	—	12.3	6.9	0.2

TABLE 2. EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE REACTION RATE

Diol	$10^3 k(M^{-2}sec^{-1})$				ΔH^* kcal/mole	ΔS^* e.u.
	30°C	35°C	40°C	45°C		
1,3-Propane	16.2	26.8	44.0	69.3	18.2	-7.2
1,3-Butane	17.7	26.8	44.8	69.5	18.2	-7.2
2-Methyl-2,4-pentane	4.4	7.6	13.3	22.3	20.3	-3.1

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Discussion

The effect of manganese (II) on the oxidation of these diols is similar to that observed in 1,2 diols¹. Thus in this case also the active oxidising species are both Mn(III) and Mn(IV), latter playing the major role. The acidity dependence of the reaction rate is different from that observed in 1,2 diols¹. This is rather surprising and no satisfactory explanation is presently available. However, 1,2- and 1,3-diols are different classes of compounds and such variations in the acidity dependence is well known in several oxidation reactions e.g., oxidation of 1,2-diols³ and 1,3-diols⁴ by quinquevalent vanadium show similar differences in acidity dependence.

Activation parameters suggest that the oxidation of 1,3-diols also involve rupture of a C-C bond as in the case of 1,2-diols. The formation of carbonyl compounds also supports this conclusion. The following mechanism may then be suggested.

The first step is the rapid reversible formation of complex between the diol and Mn(III) or Mn(IV) respectively, followed by the rate determining step.

In acid permanganate solution in equilibrium with atmospheric oxygen (not excluded in the experiments) Mn(II) are produced by the dynamic equilibrium⁵ :

This accounts for initial Mn(II) formation.

followed by steps (6) and (7).

The oxidation of 1,3-butanediol is slightly slower than that of 1,3-propanediol but the oxidation of 2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol is much slower than those of the other diols. This may be due to the inductive effect of three methyl groups in α -position to the hydroxyl groups in 2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol. The inductive effect of a -CH₂ group is considerably less than that of three methyl groups and this may explain the relative resistance of 2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol to the oxidation.

References

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